

EffBT: An Efficient Behavior Tree Reactive Synthesis and Execution Framework

Anonymous Author(s)*

Abstract—Behavior Trees (BTs), originated from the control of Non-Player-Characters (NPCs), have been widely embraced in robotics and software engineering communities due to their modularity, reactivity, and other beneficial characteristics. It is highly desirable to synthesize BTs automatically. The consequent challenges are to ensure the generated BTs semantically correct, well-structured, and efficiently executable. To address these challenges, in this paper, we present a novel reactive synthesis method for BTs, namely EffBT, to generate correct and efficient controllers from formal specifications in GR(1) automatically. The idea is to construct BTs soundly from the intermediate strategies derived during the algorithm of GR(1) realizability check. Additionally, we introduce pruning strategies and use of *Parallel* nodes to improve BT execution, while none of the priors explored before. We prove the soundness of the EffBT method, and experimental results across various scenarios and datasets demonstrate its effectiveness.

Index Terms—Behavior Trees, Reactive Synthesis, GR(1), Efficient Execution

I. INTRODUCTION

Behavior Trees (BTs), initially developed for controlling Non-Player Characters (NPCs), have gained significant popularity in robotics due to their advantages in modularity, reactivity, and other features. Moreover, they are also a powerful tool in software engineering, particularly in domains where complex decision-making and control logic are required. They play a key role in organizing, controlling, and executing complex behaviors in a modular and maintainable way, and provide the programming framework for component-based system and software design. BTs excel in environments requiring reactive systems, task prioritization, and failure management. As robotic and software systems become more and more complex, the most desirable goal for developers is to automatically design BTs. In the past decades, researchers have worked a lot to search for solutions, lots of methods, including evolution algorithms [1][2], reinforcement learning [3], task and motion planning [4], Large Language Models [5][6], and learning from demonstrations [7][8], have been used to generate BTs for solving a variety of tasks. Compared with those informal methods mentioned above, reactive synthesis, which automatically obtains correct-by-construction representations (e.g., automaton) from formal specifications (e.g., Linear Temporal Logic (LTL)), has also been used in BTs' synthesis. It has a significant advantage in that its outcomes are rigorously aligned with the provided formal specifications.

There are two main categories in terms of BTs' reactive synthesis. The first, such as TAMP [4], utilizes a model-checking-based strategy on general LTL and suggests synthesizing BTs from an emptiness-checking procedure over product automata,

which is the production of the Büchi automata (converted from the negation of LTL specifications) and a transition system (describes the robot and environment). If the specification is satisfiable, the procedure identifies a counter-example path (i.e., a state transition path), and then constructs BTs from it. Nevertheless, the conversion from LTL to Büchi automata exhibits exponential time complexity, implying that the conversion time grows exponentially with the size of the formula. Consequently, approaches relying on this strategy inevitably face the challenge of high computational complexity (at least EXPTIME). The second category, based on the Fragment of LTL (F-LTL), obtains BTs from F-LTL specifications rather than general LTL to reduce the complexity. In previous studies [9][10], authors restrict formulas to specific LTL patterns and then derive transition strategies by calculating the value functions, requirement functions, and constraint functions for each formula. Following that, the final BTs can be constructed by encoding and assembling the results of these functions.

In addition, two indirect methods are identified for constructing BTs from GR(1) in our paper, termed NaiveBT and RawBT, respectively. We utilize them for comparison and point out their drawbacks in the structure and execution of BTs through experimental and theoretical analysis. Aside from this, an extra alternative method involves transforming the specification into an automaton and then obtaining BTs from it. However, BTs are action-based structures while automata are state-based, making it challenging to identify meaningful actions during the construction. This difficulty arises due to the complexity of states and state transitions in automata.

In this work, we propose a novel GR(1)-based behavior tree synthesis framework, termed EffBT. Given a GR(1) specification, our method regards it as a game structure that encapsulates the system and environment dynamics along with a GR(1) formula that describes the objectives. Then, EffBT checks its realizability and stores transition strategies if realizable [11]. We intend to directly extract BTs from these intermediates. However, it is not straightforward due to the following two challenges: building semantically correct and well-structured BTs, and improving their execution efficiency. For the first challenge, we decompose and restructure the intermediate strategies, then modularly construct corresponding subtrees and combine them. For the second challenge, we propose pruning strategies and the use of *Parallel* nodes to improve BT execution, an approach not previously explored. Subsequently, we prove the soundness of the EffBT method.

The EffBT also falls into the second category of synthesizing from LTL fragments like the priors [9][10]. However,

our method differs significantly from theirs in not only the specification language (aka GR(1) vs specific formula patterns) but also the approach to construct BTs and their optimization. First, our method adopts GR(1) realizability check as the unified procedure of transition calculating rather than performing individual function calculations for each formula pattern, which makes intermediate results more regular. Then, benefiting from this, we introduce a more structured BT construction approach compared to priors. In our approach, each subtree features a similar sub-structure but is responsible for addressing distinct subgoals. This design not only aligns with the expertise gained from manually designing behavior trees in large quantities, but also ensures that the BTs exhibit superior modularity, better readability, and are much more convenient for debugging. Furthermore, to enhance the execution performance of generated BTs, we investigate and propose the design principle of using *Parallel* nodes.

To our knowledge, few priors focused on structural optimization for improving the execution efficiency of BTs, and none of them utilizes *Parallel* nodes. In the design of BTs, pursuing a concise and modular tree structure is a goal worth striving for: Firstly, a concise structure with fewer nodes and shorter paths helps the efficiency of the decision-making process, which is crucial for hard real-time systems whose overheads should be reduced as required. Secondly, modular BTs are generally easier to understand and reuse, which is essential for team collaboration and knowledge transfer. It is deserved to construct BTs correctly and keep the results concise and modular simultaneously.

The primary contributions of this work can be summarized as follows:

- We propose an algorithm for the direct construction of well-structured BTs from the intermediates of the GR(1), and we further prove the soundness of our method.
- We optimize the execution efficiency of generated BTs by employing pruning strategies and incorporating *Parallel* nodes when construction.
- We substantiate the effectiveness of our method through experimental evaluations compared to NaiveBT, RawBT, as well as two representative GR(1) synthesis methods Spectra [12] and JITS [13], conducted across various tasks and datasets.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Sec. II provides necessary backgrounds on BTs and GR(1) synthesis. Sec. III presents the NaiveBT and the RawBT methods. Sec. IV gives the problem formulation and introduces our method in detail, along with soundness proof and complexity analysis. Sec. V contains the experimental research questions, configurations, results, and analysis. Finally, Sec. VI recalls prior studies, and Sec. VII concludes this paper.

II. PRELIMINARIES

A. Behavior Trees

Behavior Trees (BTs) are rooted directed trees whose running starts from the root node, and a *tick* signal is transited to

Fig. 1: A simplified Work Pieces (WP) Welding BT.

its children following the depth-first order. Each node in BTs has three types of status, *Running*, *Success*, or *Failure*, and returns one of the statuses to its parent when being ticked.

The leaf nodes (also known as *Execution* nodes) include *Condition* (as the ellipse nodes in Fig. 1) and *Action* nodes (as the gray box node in Fig. 1). *Condition* nodes have no *Running* status and return *Success* only when the condition stands. *Action* nodes start execution when they are been ticked, return *Success* when actions performs successfully, *Failure* when actions failed, else return *Running*.

The non-leaf nodes (also known as *ControlFlow* nodes) include the *Sequence*, the *Selector*, and the *Parallel* nodes (as the marks with an \rightarrow in a green box, an $?$ in a yellow box, and an \Rightarrow in a blue box shown in Fig. 1, resp.), whose statuses depend on their type and statuses of their children. When *Sequence* is ticked, it ticks its children from left to right until any child returns *Failure* then the *Sequence* fail, or all of the children return *Success* in that case *Sequence* succeeds also, or otherwise it returns *Running* (i.e., any one child is running). When *Selector* is ticked, *tick* signals are routed to its children in the same manner with *Sequence* until any child returns *Success* and the *Selector* succeeds, or all of the children failed which leading to the *Selector* fails, or otherwise return *Running*. Note that *Sequence/Selector* nodes will not pass *tick* signals to the next children (if any) when the previous child returns *Failure/Success* or *Running*. In terms of the *Parallel*, let n and m denote the total number of its children and the threshold defined by users, it ticks all its children simultaneously and returns *Success* if m children succeed, *Failure* if $n - m + 1$ children fail, and *Running* in other cases.

Usually, during the execution of BTs, a *blackboard* is built for variable sharing (e.g., sensor information) among nodes, which operates a dictionary with keys and values, and allows all the nodes in BTs to read from and write to it.

B. The GR(1) Synthesis

GR(1) synthesis is originally devised to solve the problem of automatically generating digital designs from linear-time specifications [11]. Specifically, it takes GR(1) specifications as input and yields correct-by-construction controllers (e.g., Fair Discrete System (FDS)). The GR(1) specification ψ defined on atomic propositions of environment and system variables (\mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} , resp.) contains initial assumptions and guarantees which restrict initial states (θ_e and θ_s , resp.), safety assumptions and guarantees that describe the transition from current to next state (ρ_e and ρ_s , resp.), and justice assumptions and guarantees that require an assertion holds infinitely many times during a computation (J^e and J^s , resp.), in which a *state* is an

198 assignment to $\mathcal{X} \cup \mathcal{Y}$, assumptions denote possible states of the
 199 environment, and guarantees describe the system's reactions to
 200 those states. $\varphi = \bigwedge_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \mathcal{GF}J_i^e \rightarrow \bigwedge_{j \in \{1, \dots, n\}} \mathcal{GF}J_j^s$
 201 is called GR(1) formula which is a fragment of LTL that suits
 202 for describing most reactive systems. Prior works [11][13] are
 203 recommended for further reading about the GR(1) specifica-
 204 tion and synthesis.

205 1) *Realizability Check of GR(1)*: This procedure checks
 206 whether the given GR(1) specification ψ is realizable, and
 207 this problem is formulated as an equivalent two-player game
 208 between system and environment [11]. The game structure GS
 209 is a tuple $\langle \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}, \theta_e, \theta_s, \rho_e, \rho_s \rangle$ constructed from the GR(1)
 210 specification, where $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{X} \cup \mathcal{Y}$, θ_e, θ_s are initial assumptions
 211 and guarantees, ρ_e, ρ_s are transition assumptions and guaran-
 212 tees. Then, the given GR(1) specification is realizable if and
 213 only if (iff) the system wins the game, and the system winning
 214 condition of this game is GR(1) formula φ , i.e., regardless of
 215 how the environment changes, the system can find a way to
 216 continue the game, and the path of the game conforms to φ .
 217 System-winning set W_s (or z) is a set of states that starts
 218 from which system-winning strategies always exist. Hence, the
 219 specification is realizable iff W_s is not an empty set. Then,
 220 to determine the system-winning set W_s , we should resolve
 221 its equivalent problem, namely calculating the semantics of the
 222 following μ -calculus formula over game structure GS
 223 achieved through a three-level fixed point calculation:

$$W_s = \nu Z \left(\bigwedge_{j \in \{1, \dots, n\}} \mu Y \left(\bigvee_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \nu X (J_j^s \wedge \odot Z \vee \odot Y \vee \neg J_i^e \wedge \odot X) \right) \right)$$

224 where $\odot \varphi$ denotes the controlled predecessor, from the
 225 states in which the system can force the environment to visit
 226 a state in φ . Symbols μ and ν denote the minimum and the
 227 maximum fix-point operator, respectively. Symbols X, Y , and
 228 Z are relation variables that are assigned as *true*, *false* and
 229 *true* initially. During the calculation, two crucial intermediate
 230 arrays that entail system transition strategies, $mX[j][r][i]$ and
 231 $mY[j][r]$, are stored. Here, $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, $r \in \{1, \dots, k\}$, and
 232 $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, where the variables n, k , and m denote the
 233 counts of system guarantees, the iteration times for calculating
 234 μY , and the counts of environment assumptions, respectively.

235 $mX[j][r][i]$ is the fix-point calculation results of the innermost
 236 safety game, i.e., the maximum fix-point νX . Intuitively, from
 237 the states in $mX[j][r][i]$, the system could either move one
 238 step closer to reaching $J_j^s \wedge \odot Z$ states within r transitions
 239 to satisfy the j th system guarantee, or keep forcing the
 240 environment to violate the i th environmental assumption J_i^e
 241 which violates the left part of the GR(1) formula.

242 $mY[j][r]$ stores the fix-point calculation results of the inner
 243 least reachability game, i.e., the minimum fix-point μY , which
 244 assures that the game can reach $J_j^s \wedge \odot Z_{j \oplus 1}$ states finally.
 245 From the states in $mY[j][r]$, the system could either move
 246 to $J_j^s \wedge \odot Z$ states within r steps that satisfy the j th system
 247 guarantee or violate at least one environment assumption J_i^e
 248 for some i .

Moreover, the outermost maximum fix-point νZ ensures 249
 that once reaching J_j^s states, the system proceeds to visit $J_{j \oplus 1}^s$ 250
 states and keeps the looping to fulfill all justice guarantees. 251

2) *FDS Construction in GR(1)*: Following the original 252
 process of GR(1) synthesis, static Fair Discrete System (FDS) 253
 controllers defined as $\langle \mathcal{V}_D, \theta_D, \rho \rangle$ will be constructed from 254
 $mX[j][r][i]$ and $mY[j][r]$ immediately after the realizability check, 255
 in which $\mathcal{V}_D = \mathcal{V} \cup jx$, $\theta_D = \theta_e \rightarrow (\theta_s \wedge (jx = 1) \wedge z)$ that 256
 restricts initial states. The extra variable set jx represents the 257
 index of some justice goal the system is aiming to accomplish. 258

Intuitively, the transition ρ in FDS has three parts ρ_1, ρ_2 , and 259
 ρ_3 , each tailored to handling a separate case. When the current 260
 is a z state, the first part ρ_1 deals and marks jx to the next 261
 $jx \oplus 1$, and the next state is from z (e.g., a random state in it). 262
 The second part ρ_2 takes efforts when the current state is an 263
 $mY[j][r]$ state, then the system moves to $mY[j][r-1]$ that is 264
 closer to satisfying J_j^s . When the current is a $mX[j][r][i]$ state, 265
 the strategy ρ_3 works but still stays in $mX[j][r][i]$ states. Their 266
 formal representations are as follows, where the transition ρ 267
 in FDS equals $\rho_1 \vee \rho_2 \vee \rho_3$. 268

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_1 &= \bigvee_{j \in \{1, \dots, n\}} (jx = j) \wedge z \wedge J_j^s \wedge \rho_e \wedge \rho_s \wedge z' \wedge (jx' = j + 1) \\ \rho_2 &= \bigvee_{j \in \{1, \dots, n\}} (jx = jx' = j) \wedge \rho_2(j) \\ \rho_2(j) &= \bigvee_{r > 1} mY[j][r] \wedge \neg mY[j][< r] \wedge \rho_e \wedge \rho_s \wedge mY'[j][< r] \\ \rho_3 &= \bigvee_{j \in \{1, \dots, n\}} (jx = jx' = j) \wedge \rho_3(j) \\ \rho_3(j) &= \bigvee_{r > 1} \bigvee_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}} mX[j][r][i] \wedge \neg mX[j][< (r, i)] \wedge \neg J_i^e \\ &\quad \wedge \rho_e \wedge \rho_s \wedge mX'[j][r][i] \end{aligned}$$

269 III. THE NAIVEBT AND THE RAWBT METHODS

In this section, we briefly introduce the NaiveBT and the 270
 RawBT methods. We also explain their inherent limitations 271
 through theoretical analysis and later experiments. 272

273 A. The NaiveBT Method

Tracing the **Brown Arrow** in Fig. 2, the following steps 274
 outline the procedure of the NaiveBT method for synthesizing 275
 BTs from GR(1): Step 1 and 2 conduct realizability check 276
 over (GS, φ) and construct FDS, similar to the original GR(1) 277
 synthesis; Then, Step 3 transforms the FDS into an If-Then- 278
 Else (ITE) structure [14] as it is stored as a BDD; Finally, 279
 Step 4 constructs a BT which is straightforward due to the 280
 sufficient capacity of BTs to cover the ITE logic. The first three 281
 steps have already been proposed and implemented in [11] 282
 and [14]. Limited to the pages, the detailed introduction of 283
 Step 4 about how to construct BTs from ITE by matching 284
 regular patterns and applying transition rules is in the supple- 285
 mentary materials [15]. 286

287 B. The RawBT Method

Following the **Blue Arrow** in Fig. 2, the RawBT is also a 288
 FDS-based BTs' synthesis method but without transforming to 289

Fig. 2: Procedure Overview of the NaiveBT (Brown Arrow), RawBT (Blue Arrow), and EffBT (Green Arrow) Methods

ITEs. In detail, it obtains BTs from the transition strategy ρ in FDS in a top-down manner (Step 3'). For ρ_1, ρ_2 and ρ_3 in the transition, we formulate their corresponding subtrees by substituting the outermost disjunctions with *Selector* nodes, and conjunct these ρ -subtrees by *Selector* as root. Regarding the innermost conjunction formulas, we identify and separate the action and condition according to whether the predication describes the current or the next state following it. For example, the minimum part of ρ_1 is $(jx=j) \wedge z \wedge J_j^2 \wedge \rho \wedge z' \wedge (jx'=j+1)$, which corresponds to the node *Condition* $((jx=j) \wedge z \wedge J_j^2 \wedge \rho)$ and the node *Action* $(z'_{\mathcal{X}} \wedge (jx'=j+1))$, where $z'_{\mathcal{X}}$ is a systematic z' state that only preserves those predicates of system variables. We then combine them with *Sequence* and mount the subtree under the corresponding *Selector* node in ρ -subtrees. However, after observing the execution of such BTs, we introduce the following finding. The detailed proof of this property is available in [15].

Proposition 1. *State transitions in a single sub-strategy (i.e., to reach a particular justice goal) significantly exceed those between different sub-strategies.*

Each BT produced by RawBT has three subtrees that correspond to ρ_1, ρ_2 , and ρ_3 transitions in FDS. As per Prop. 1, state transitions predominantly happen in reaching justice goals, but the parts of reaching a single goal are distributed among those subtrees. Consequently, during execution, BTs must frequently tick and switch to find the proper subtree in different subtrees, which is a process that wastes lots of time in decision-making. In our approach, we addressed this limitation by introducing a novel structural design and utilizing *Parallel* nodes.

IV. METHODOLOGY

We propose EffBT, a method for constructing BTs from GR(1) that solves the aforementioned challenges and overcomes the limitations inherent in NaiveBT and RawBT.

A. Problem Formulation

Recall that \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} denote the environment and system variables, respectively. The set of all variables $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{X} \cup \mathcal{Y}$. The set of all states is denoted by S , where each state $s \in S$ is an assignment to \mathcal{V} . The GR(1) specification ψ can be decomposed into a game structure GS and a GR(1) formula φ . Subsequently, we present the discrete definition of BTs.

Definition (Behavior Tree). A BT is a tuple $\mathcal{T} = \langle f, r \rangle$, where $f : gud \rightarrow dst$ describes its effects in system states. Here, $gud : 2^{\mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{X}'}$ and $dst : 2^{\mathcal{Y}'}$ denotes the transition guards and the destination system states, resp. The mapping $r : 2^{\mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{V}'} \rightarrow \{S, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{F}\}$ represents the return status.

An execution of a BT over GS is an infinite state sequence $\sigma = s_0, s_1, \dots$, where s_0 is the initial state. A transition from s_i to s_{i+1} is legal iff $s_i \cup s_{i+1}|_{\mathcal{X}} \models gud$ and $s_{i+1}|_{\mathcal{Y}} \models dst$, where $s_{i+1}|_{\mathcal{X}}$ denotes the environment state only contains \mathcal{X} and excluding system variables \mathcal{Y} . A BT satisfies a GR(1) specification iff all of its executions satisfy ψ , denoted as $BT \models \psi$. Given these preliminaries, the BT synthesis problem is formally defined as follows:

Problem. *Given a GR(1) specification ψ , the problem is to automatically construct a BT \mathcal{T} that satisfies ψ , i.e., $\mathcal{T} \models \psi$.*

B. The BT Construction Algorithm in EffBT

1) *Overview:* As depicted in Fig. 2 (following the Green Arrow), our framework consists of two main procedures. The first, as detailed in Sec.II-B, checks the realizability of GR(1) specifications. In this section, we focus on presenting our algorithm (Step 2'), which constructs correct BTs from the results of Step 1. Moreover, it refines the structure of subtrees to mitigate the shortcomings in RawBT and overcome the first challenge.

In addition to basic *ControlFlow* nodes, as summarized in Table. I, leaf nodes in the result BTs contain three types, including *Condition* node *Cond*, and two *Action* nodes *CalAct* and *MovAct*. Note that an extra *Action Library* is required in *MovAct*, as well as for the $A^{P'}$ in NaiveBT, and the *Action()* in RawBT, when the goal is to control actual movements, e.g., a robot arm in reality. This is because our method is incapable of synthesizing primitive controllers (e.g., PID controllers), which is a common abstraction in reactive synthesis. Intuitively, the *Action Library* stores the action name and variables as key and its actual primitive action controller as value, which will be dynamically matched and loaded when execution.

TABLE I: Predefined Condition and Action Types

Name (Abbr.)	Description
Cond	It assesses whether its inner condition are satisfied, returns <i>Success</i> if true, or <i>Failure</i> otherwise.
CalAct	This action conducts pure computation and has no actual movement, return <i>Failure</i> when its result is <i>false</i> or invalid.
MovAct	This action matches the primitive function in <i>Action Library</i> and conducts action in physical or simulated environments.

The pseudo-code of BTs' construction algorithm in EffBT is shown in Alg. 1 and Alg. 2. This procedure takes as input the intermediates and results ($mX[[]][[]]$, $mY[[]][[]]$, and z) from GR(1) realizability check, along with an auxiliary variable set jx which identifies sub-strategies. Then it generates the result behavior tree BT_{eff} that satisfies φ whose root applies

Fig. 3: Overview of the Structure of the BT from EffBT

372 the *Parallel* (c.f., line 1 in Alg. 1). Figure. 3 demonstrates
 373 an overview of the structure of BT_{eff} , it has n structurally
 374 similar *Sequence* subtrees and the j th one referred as $subBT_j$.
 375 Intuitively, each subtree corresponds to a sub-strategy that
 376 controls the system to satisfy one particular justice guar-
 377 antee (goal), and we construct n subtrees for all goals. A single
 378 subtree $subBT_j$ is composed of three parts: a *Cond* node to
 379 judge whether the current goal is the j th justice guarantee; a
 380 *CalAct* node to ensure both systems and environments satisfy
 381 the transition rules $\rho_e \wedge \rho_s$ (c.f., line 4 in Alg. 1); and a *Parallel*
 382 subtree BT_ρ with three children that represent the ρ_1, ρ_2 , and
 383 ρ_3 transitions. Note that the ρ_x transitions discussed here only
 384 correspond to a single justice guarantee that differs from those
 385 in Sec. II-B2. To distinguish, we denote them as BT_{ρ_1}, BT_{ρ_2} ,
 386 and BT_{ρ_3} , each of them differs in structures and meanings.
 387 By decomposing the original transitions, we can categorize
 388 ρ_x transitions associated with the j th justice goal into a single
 389 subtree and avoid the decision-making problem in the RawBT
 390 method.

391 Besides, an internal blackboard is designed to store running
 392 statuses (e.g., the j th subtree currently active, system and
 393 environment states) and intermediate calculation results from
 394 *CalAct*, which is transparent to users. During the execution,
 395 the environment and system states are continuously perceived
 396 and logged onto this blackboard. Based on this information,
 397 BTs determine the subsequent actions to be taken.

398 2) *Construction of BT_{ρ_1} and BT_{ρ_2}* : As shown in Fig. 4(a),
 399 the j th ρ_1 subtree BT_{ρ_1} is constructed as *Sequence* with *Cond*
 400 and *MovAct* as its children (c.f., line 19 to 20 in Alg. 1). The
 401 instanced *Cond* checks whether the current state satisfies the
 402 j th justice goal, if true, next the instanced *MovAct* node takes
 403 action to the $j \oplus 1$ goal.

Fig. 4: The Inner Structure of BT_{ρ_1} and BT_{ρ_2}

404 As presented in Fig. 4(b), the BT_{ρ_2} is constructed as a
 405 *Selector* with many *Sequence* subtrees (referred as $tree_{\rho_2}$), each
 406 subtree has the same structure with BT_{ρ_1} but differs in contents
 407 (c.f., line 8 to 18 in Alg. 1). Intuitively, the *Cond* under the
 408 r th $tree_{\rho_2}$ checks whether current state satisfies $mY[j][r]$, if
 409 true, then the *MovAct* forces the system to $mY[j][r-1]$ states
 410 that one step closer to the j th goal and finally reach the goal.

Algorithm 1 BT Construction of the EffBT Method

Input: $mX[\square\square\square], mY[\square], z, jx$

Output: BT_{eff} — the root node of the result BT

```

1:  $BT_{eff} \leftarrow$  Parallel Node
2: for all  $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$  do
3:    $subBT_j \leftarrow$  Sequence Node;
4:    $subBT_j.addChildren(\{Cond(jx=j?), CalAct(\rho_e \wedge \rho_s)\})$ 
5:    $BT_\rho \leftarrow$  Parallel Node
   /*Construction of the  $j$ th sub-tree  $BT_{\rho_3}^j$ */
6:    $BT_{\rho_3}^j \leftarrow ConstructTree_3(mX[\square\square\square], z, j)$ 
7:    $BT_\rho.addChildIfNotEmpty(BT_{\rho_3}^j)$   $\triangleright$  Prune (Case 2).
   /*Construction of the  $j$ th sub-tree  $BT_{\rho_2}^j$ */
8:    $BT_{\rho_2}^j \leftarrow$  Parallel Node;  $low \leftarrow mY[j][0]$ 
9:   for all  $r \in \{2, \dots, r_j\}$  do
10:     $cond \leftarrow mY[j][r] \wedge \neg low \wedge low'_{\mathcal{X}}$ 
11:    if  $cond \neq false$  then  $\triangleright$  Prune (Case 1).
12:       $tree_{\rho_2} \leftarrow Sequence.addChild(Cond(cond))$ 
13:       $tree_{\rho_2}.addChild(MovAct(low'_{\mathcal{Y}} \wedge jx' = j))$ 
14:       $BT_{\rho_2}.addChild(tree_{\rho_2})$ 
15:    end if
16:     $low \leftarrow low \vee mY[j][r]$ 
17:  end for
18:   $BT_\rho.addChildIfNotEmpty(BT_{\rho_2}^j)$   $\triangleright$  Prune (Case 2).
   /*Construction of the  $j$ th sub-tree  $BT_{\rho_1}^j$ */
19:   $BT_{\rho_1}^j \leftarrow Sequence.addChild(Cond(jx = j \wedge z \wedge J_j^s \wedge z'_{\mathcal{X}}))$ 
20:   $BT_{\rho_1}^j.addChild(MovAct(z'_{\mathcal{Y}} \wedge jx' = j + 1))$ 
21:  if  $subBT_j.hasNoChild()$  then  $\triangleright$  Prune (Case 2).
22:     $subBT_j \leftarrow BT_{\rho_1}$ 
23:  else if  $n = 1$  then  $\triangleright$  Prune (Case 2).
24:     $BT_{eff} \leftarrow subBT_1$ 
25:  else
26:     $subBT_j.addChild(BT_\rho)$ 
27:     $BT_{eff}.addChild(subBT_j)$ 
28:  end if
29: end for

```

411 3) *Construction of BT_{ρ_3}* : The construction of BT_{ρ_3} is pre-
 412 sented in Alg. 2, and its structure is shown in Fig. 5(a). It
 413 is constructed as a *Selector* with two-level nested *Sequence*
 414 subtrees for each r and i (c.f., line 3 to line 20 in Alg. 2).
 415 Moreover, for the lowermost subtree, which is also structurally
 416 similar to BT_{ρ_1} , its instanced *Cond* node checks whether the
 417 current state satisfies $mX[j][r][i]$, if true, the *MovAct* force
 418 the system stays to keep violating the i th environment assumption.

C. The Optimizations to EffBT

419 The execution of BTs can unfold in dual stages: decision-
 420 make and action-take. The *tick* signal propagates through
 421 nodes to select the next action during the decision-make phase.
 422 Then a leaf node executes the chosen action during the action-
 423 take phase, such as moving or grabbing in simulated or phys-
 424 ical environments. In this part, we propose pruning strategies
 425 and incorporate *Parallel* nodes to improve the execution speed
 426 of BTs, more specifically, by decreasing decision-making time.
 427

428 1) *Pruning*: We prune useless nodes or subtrees during the
 429 construction in two cases. The first, when constructing subtrees

Algorithm 2 Construction of j th BT_{ρ_3} - $ConstructTree_3()$ **Input:** $mX[\cdot][\cdot][\cdot]$, z , j **Output:** $BT_{\rho_3}^j$ — the root node of this tree

```

1:  $BT_{\rho_3}^j \leftarrow$  Selector Node
2:  $low \leftarrow false$ 
3: for all  $r \in \{1, \dots, r_j\}$  do
4:    $tree_{\rho_3} \leftarrow$  Sequence Node
5:   for all  $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$  do
6:      $cond \leftarrow mX[j][r][i] \wedge \neg low \wedge mX'_{\mathcal{Y}}[j][r][i]$ 
7:      $act \leftarrow mX'_{\mathcal{X}}[j][r][i] \wedge jx' = j$ 
8:     if  $cond \neq false$  then  $\triangleright$  Prune (Case 1).
9:       if  $m = 1$  then  $\triangleright$  Prune (Case 2).
10:       $tree_{\rho_3}.addChild(Cond(cond))$ 
11:       $tree_{\rho_3}.addChild(MovAct(act))$ 
12:    else
13:       $sub_{\rho_3} \leftarrow$  Sequence.addChild(Cond(cond))
14:       $sub_{\rho_3}.addChild(MovAct(act))$ 
15:       $tree_{\rho_3}.addChild(sub_{\rho_3})$ 
16:    end if
17:  end if
18:   $low \leftarrow low \vee mX[j][r][i]$ 
19: end for
20:  $BT_{\rho_3}.addChild(tree_{\rho_3})$ 
21: end for
22: return  $BT_{\rho_3}$ 

```

of BT_{ρ_2} and BT_{ρ_3} (i.e., $tree_{\rho_2}$ and $tree_{\rho_3}$), if the condition is false (c.f., line 11 in Alg. 1, line 7 in Alg. 2), the subtree will be pruned as it will never be executed. The second case occurs if a *ControlFlow* node has only one child, we remove it and reload its child to its parent directly. As shown in Fig. 5(a), if the *Sequence* in level-2 has just one child, it will be pruned (c.f., line 8 to line 11 in Alg. 2) and the result is shown in Fig. 5(b). Besides, the second strategy is also applied in the construction of BT_{ρ_1} , BT_{ρ_2} , and the whole tree (c.f., line 7, line 18 and line 21 to 28 in Alg. 1).

Fig. 5: The Inner and Pruned Structure of BT_{ρ_3}

2) *Adoption of Parallel Nodes*: Parallelism is always being pursued in computing even if it can be simulated by interleaving. Because it would be a better choice to keep the parallel nature in both the problem and solution. Besides, with the increasing application of multi-core processors, the parallel is much desired and feasible in many domains such as robotics.

We adopt the *Parallel* ($m=1$) as an alternative to *Selector*. They share similar semantics, with success being determined by the success of any child node. However, *Parallel* executes its children in parallel, which would be faster than *Selector* whose children execute one by one, and later experiments have

verified the effectiveness. To our knowledge, none of the priors focused on the efficiency of BTs' execution and none of them utilizes *Parallel* nodes. It is nontrivial since potential conflicts need to be solved. Thus, we identify possible conflict situations during BTs' construction and summarize them as principles in Prop. 2. To use *Parallel* unambiguously, any BT violating the rules should not use *Parallel* as root, more details are presented in the additional materials [15].

Proposition 2. A BT could adopt *Parallel* ($m=1$) as a new root if satisfies the following conditions: 1. its root is an *Selector*; 2. no blackboard written conflict or simultaneous condition and action among its children.

Owing to the regularity of GR(1) formulas, our algorithm, particularly the modularized and unified subtree construction and the usage of the auxiliary variable jx , could synthesize BTs with superior structure and is capable of employing *Parallel* nodes, while priors have difficulties blamed on their structure design. For example, the BT in [9] is a *Sequence* as root with several *Sequence* subtrees (BT_n , $n \in \{2, \dots, 6\}$), and the deepest subtrees (e.g., BT_{2i}) uses *Selector* as root with both *Condition* and *Action* nodes as children. However, replacing the *Selector* with a *Parallel* would lead to simultaneous condition check and action conduct when executing BT, which is not reasonable obviously.

By the way, it is also feasible to use *Parallel* in the RawBT method (termed RawBT-P) as a substitute for the *Sequence* between the three ρ -transition subtrees, which has a limited effect on the structure of BTs, except for the nodes' replacement. As for the execution performance of BTs, we argue that the adoption of *Parallel* in RawBT could bring an improvement since they tick their children simultaneously, which effectively shortens the decision-making time. However, it is still unable to match the performance of EffBT. As per Prop. 1, state transitions in a single sub-strategy (i.e., to reach a particular justice goal) significantly exceed those between different sub-strategies. Hence, RawBT-P encounters identical challenges as RawBT, i.e., it also requires frequent ticking and switching between the three ρ -transitions to determine the appropriate one among different subtrees. Overall, the final efficiency result would belike: EffBT > RawBT-P > RawBT.

D. An Example of BT Construction and Execution

A simple example of constructing BTs using EffBT is provided in the supplementary materials [15]. In this part, we demonstrate the execution of synthesized BTs. As depicted in Fig. 6(a), the root (*Parallel*) receives a *tick* signal in the beginning and then ticks all its children. This signal will be transported to each subtree and then the leftmost children $Cond(jx = j)$, $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. When ticked, these nodes query the inner blackboard for the value of jx , check whether is currently running at the j th subtree and only one subtree would return *Running*. Then on the second tick (see Fig. 6(b)), the running subtree ticks its next child $CalAct(\rho_e \wedge \rho_s)$ that calculates the conjunction of current state, movements of

Fig. 6: Execution of BTs generated by the EffBT Method

environment, and $\rho_e \wedge \rho_s$ verify the legality of the transitions and writes the results to blackboard with key *mediate*.

After this, on the third tick (see Fig. 6(c)), the last part of the subtree is ticked, which then ticks all its children (BT_{ρ_1} , BT_{ρ_2} , and BT_{ρ_3}) simultaneously. Each BT_{ρ_x} handles different cases as we have introduced before and only one MovAct node will be finally executed. Take BT_{ρ_1} as an instance, it ticks its child Cond to judge whether the current is a $z \wedge J_j^s$ state at first, which calculates the conjunction of the *mediate* in inner blackboard and the BDD in itself, returns *Failure* if the result is *false*, or otherwise returns *Success* and updates the value of *mediate* with the result. If succeeded, the MovAct will be executed which matches and takes action (in Action Library) to make the system state to $z' \wedge jx' = j \oplus 1$. Behaviors of the other two subtrees (BT_{ρ_2} and BT_{ρ_3}) are similar. Note that we stored the auxiliary variable jx in the blackboard and each active subtree updates it to $jx \oplus 1$ upon success, thus, the root (*Parallel*) behaves similarly to *ControlFlow* nodes with memory, and the entire BT is executed in sequence cyclically.

E. Correctness and Complexity

Theorem. *EffBT is a sound method, whenever a given GR(1) specification ψ is realizable, the final BT_{eff} can be correctly constructed, i.e., $BT_{\text{eff}} \models \psi$.*

Intuitively, to prove the soundness, we should prove that the dynamics of BT_{eff} subset to the FDS from the general GR(1), since that the GR(1) synthesis is both sound and complete [11]. Then, we formally present the proofs as outlined below.

Proof. We explain the dynamics of BT_{eff} by extracting its effect $f = \mathcal{F}[[BT_{\text{eff}}]]$, which equals $\bigvee_{j \in \{1, \dots, n\}} \mathcal{F}[[subBT_j]]$ because BT_{eff} is composed of n separate subtrees, and $\mathcal{F}[[\cdot]]$ is the effect calculate function. The disjunction of two effects (e.g., f_i and f_j) yields an new effect that defined as $\{gud_i \vee gud_j, dst_i \vee dst_j\}$. Then, considering a single subtree $subBT_j$, its effect involves three parts from BT_{ρ_1} , BT_{ρ_2} , and BT_{ρ_3} as only the BT_{ρ_x} subtrees conducts actions and has state transitions, i.e., $\mathcal{F}[[subBT_j]] = \bigvee_{x \in \{1, \dots, 3\}} \{(jx = j) \wedge \rho_e \wedge \rho_s \wedge \mathcal{F}[[BT_{\rho_x}^j]].gud, \mathcal{F}[[BT_{\rho_x}^j]].dst\}$. Note that the conditions in Cond and CalAct are also constructed into the transition guard. Then, following the construction algorithm (c.f., Alg. 1 and Alg. 2), we present the effect calculations for each $BT_{\rho_x}^j$ (i.e., $\mathcal{F}[[BT_{\rho_x}^j]]$).

As shown in Fig. 4(a) and line 7 to line 8 in Alg. 1, $BT_{\rho_1}^j$ has the structure of a *Sequence* with Cond and MovAct as its children. This also composes to an effect with the

condition as *gud* and next state as *dst*, thus, $\mathcal{F}[[BT_{\rho_1}^j]]$ equals $\{z \wedge J_j^s, z' \wedge jx' = jx + 1\}$. As for BT_{ρ_2} , its effects are the disjunction of all its subtrees (i.e., $tree_{\rho_2}$). Besides, due to the pruning of *false* conditions, the final effect $\mathcal{F}[[BT_{\rho_2}^j]]$ equals $\bigvee_{r \in \{2, \dots, r_j\}} \{mY[j][r] \wedge \neg low, low' \wedge jx' = j\}$, where $mY[j][r] \wedge \neg low \neq false$. The effect of BT_{ρ_3} has a similar calculate algorithm with BT_{ρ_2} , which is represented as $\bigvee_{r \in \{1, \dots, r_j\}} \bigvee_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \{mX[j][r][i] \wedge \neg low, mX[j][r][i]' \wedge jx' = j\}$, where $mX[j][r][i] \wedge \neg low \neq false$.

Now, we could calculate the effect of BT_{eff} inductively by the $\mathcal{F}[[\cdot]]$ function. Subsequently, it is not difficult to find that the effect f of BT_{eff} subsets to the transition ρ in the original FDS from GR(1). Consequently, we could conclude that executions controlled by BT_{eff} always subset to executions in FDS, while $FDS \models \psi$ is sound and complete, thus, $BT_{\text{eff}} \models \psi$ is also sound. \square

Following, we discuss the complexity of our method. It consists of two procedures: the GR(1) realizability check and the BT construction. The former has a time complexity of $O(mn|\sigma|^2)$, where σ denotes the set of all variables assignments in ψ . The latter is implemented via a deepest three-level loop (c.f., Alg. 1 and Alg. 2), resulting in a complexity of $O(mnk)$. Recall that k is the iteration times for calculating μY , while m and n are the numbers of environmental assumptions and system guarantees, respectively. Consequently, the overall computational complexity of our method is the sum of these two components, i.e., $O(mn|\sigma|^2 + mnk)$, which is a polynomial complexity. Indeed, the time cost of the realizability check in our method can be quite high. However, it is worth noticing that compared to the 2EXPTIME of checking general LTL formulas, GR(1) has reduced its complexity to polynomials while retaining sufficient expressive power. Therefore, the time required for realizability checks is unavoidable and our work mainly focuses on improving the efficiency of constructing behavior trees and the efficiency of BTs' execution.

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

We implemented our method, NaiveBT, and RawBT on the GR(1) synthesis tool *Spectra*¹. Each execution node in the BT holds a small BDD, and they are combined into a whole with *ControlFlow* nodes. During execution, we utilize a blackboard implemented as a dictionary and provide basic read-and-write

¹<https://github.com/SpectraSynthesizer>

590 functionality for storing intermediates from BDD calculation.
 591 Similar to the *Spectra* tool, both BDD libraries, JTLV and
 592 CUDD, are accessible. We opted for CUDD (version 3.0) in
 593 all our experiments due to its stability. Experimental materials,
 594 including executable JAR package, specification files, and
 595 demonstration videos, can be found on Zenodo repository [15].

596 To evaluate, we have four research questions: **RQ1** How
 597 about the performance of the NaiveBT and RawBT methods?
 598 **RQ2** Does the EffBT method perform better in synthesis and
 599 BT execution? Furthermore, how does the size of specifica-
 600 tions affect its efficiency? **RQ3** How about the quality of BTs
 601 synthesized from EffBT? **RQ4** Do pruning strategies bring
 602 improvements to our method?

603 A. Scenarios and Datasets

604 1) *The FrozenLake+ Scenarios*: Figure. 7 demonstrates the
 605 Frozen Lake game in Gymnasium [16]. Initially, a player is
 606 located at the upper left corner (1,1) of a frozen lake grid world
 607 with a goal located at the far end of the world (e.g., the lower
 608 right corner (8,8) of the map). Several ice holes are distributed
 609 in the lake and the player needs to reach the goal while
 610 avoiding falling into them. Following that, we expand the
 611 initial settings to the FrozenLake+ (also denoted as Frozen⁺)
 612 by adding a beast who chases the player continuously and
 613 moves half as fast as the player. In the beginning, the beast
 614 is located at a random position next to a random goal (in
 615 Fig. 7, the beast is located at position (7,8) next to the
 616 only goal). Now, the player needs to visit all goals infinitely
 617 often while avoiding being caught and falling. Various map
 618 sizes (including 8×8, 16×16, 24×24, and 32×32) of this
 619 scenario are generated, in which the occurrence probabilities
 620 of ice holes and goals are set to 0.125 and 0.03125 respectively
 621 when generating.

Fig. 7: The Frozen⁺ scenario with 8×8 grid map

622 2) *AMBA [17] and GenBuf [18]*: Both the ARM’s AMBA
 623 AHB arbiter (AMBA) and IBM’s Generalized Buffer (Gen-
 624 Buf) from an IBM tutorial are among the most widely recog-
 625 nized GR(1) specifications for evaluation. In our experiment,
 626 the master number is set to 1, 3, 5, 7, and 9 for AMBA, while
 627 the request number is confined to 10, 30, 50, 70, and 90 for
 628 GenBuf. With the increase in counts of the masters/requests,
 629 the complexity of specifications also increases.

3) *SYNTECH Datasets [19][20]*: We opted for the SYN-
 TECH datasets for thorough evaluations of our method. It
 is a comprehensive suite of specifications that covers diverse
 ranges of tasks and owns several iterations. We selected five
 distinct versions, namely SYNTECH 15, 17, 19, 20, and 21,
 encompassing over 300 GR(1) task specifications.

B. Experimental Setups and Evaluation Metrics

All experiments are performed on a Ubuntu 22.04 computer
 equipped with an AMD Ryzen 9 5950X CPU. The maximum
 allowed time for synthesis is two hours and the maximum
 allowed memory is 2048 MB. Processes will be forcibly
 terminated if they exceed the allotted time or memory. To
 minimize the impact of JVM, all methods are executed on a
 single processor five times in each scenario and each setting,
 and the final results of evaluated metrics are the averages
 among them. Our experiments are divided into two main parts,
 along with an ablation study.

In the first part, we intend to assess the synthesis efficiency
 and the simulated execution performance of the synthesized
 outcomes. We will compare our EffBT method with RawBT,
 NaiveBT, and two representative GR(1) synthesis methods:
 the Static [12] method (denoted as Spectra) and the Just-in-
 time [13] method (denoted as JITS), respectively. Note that
 we only make the qualitative comparison to the closely related
 works [9][10] (c.f., Sec. I) due to neither of their runnable
 artifacts nor their task specifications are publicly accessible.

We execute all these methods across the aforementioned
 scenarios and datasets using identical settings. Throughout
 the construction, we record three evaluation metrics. First,
 the metric *#Nodes* denotes the sum of nodes when checking
 realizability, which indicates the scale of the problems. Then,
 the metric *Time_{RC}* records the time spent on the realizability
 check. The last metric *Construction Time* records the duration
 from the time of starting synthesis to its completion, excluding
 the time taken for realizability checks, i.e., the construction
 time of the Spectra, RawBT, and EffBT methods is the time
 spent on Step 2, Step 3’, and Step 2’ in Fig. 2 respectively.
 Note that JITS is a dynamic method that has no construction
 phase thus without construction time correspondingly.

Apart from synthesis efficiency, we then give attention to
 the execution performance of the generated results (BTs, Static
 FDS, or JITS Controllers), while few previous studies focused
 on this aspect. We execute those synthesized controllers five
 times in simulated scenarios and calculate their average. Each
 time, we measure a total decision-making time of five thousand
 steps. In each execution, the environment and system randomly
 select their next actions from a set of available options. For
 instance, in the Frozen⁺ scenario, the beast randomly chooses
 to move either up or left to chase the player, if both options
 are available, and the player then games too. Notably, the
 execution time for JITS only accounts for the step time and
 excludes the initial loading time. Additionally, we omit the
 physical action-taking time (if any, occurs in physical
 simulations or real-world scenarios). This timing involves low-
 level implementations of actual actions (e.g., the movement of

a robot arm), which are not relevant to our method, while we preserve the action-taking time used in the BDD-level updates.

Then in the second part, we evaluate the quality of the synthesized BTs from the aspects of their structures. The metric *BT Size* refers to the total number of nodes in the generated BTs, inclusive of both *ControlFlow* and *Execution* nodes. As an important advantage of BTs, modularity ensures that BTs are easy to read and reusable, hence, we introduce an additional metric to estimate this property, called *Balance*, which consists of two parts: *Structural Balance* and *Node Balance*. The former is defined as $\frac{N_{min}}{N_{max}}$, in which N_{min} and N_{max} represent the minimum and maximum node counts among the subtrees under the root. The latter is defined as $\exp(-|N_{exec}/N_{ctrl} - 2|)$, in which N_{exec} and N_{ctrl} denote the sum of *Execution* nodes and *ControlFlow* nodes, respectively. The metric *Node Balance* measures the ratio of *Execution* nodes to *ControlFlow* nodes, ideally aiming for a value close to 2. This guideline follows the manual design principles outlined in [21], which suggests that a BT with one control node and two branches is much easier to read and reuse. Both node balance and structural balance are considered better when their values are closer to 1. The metric *Balance* is defined as the sum of them.

Moreover, to address RQ4, we conduct an ablation study by disabling all pruning strategies in EffBT, forming the *EffBT#* method. We then evaluate this method and record the metrics following the same procedure as in the two main parts above. In addition, we conducted the entire experiment on *RawBT+* (the RawBT method with pruning strategies). The results of this experiment can be found in [15].

C. Synthesis Efficiency and Execution Performance Results

1) *Results of the NaiveBT Method:* Table. II demonstrates step-by-step evaluation results of the NaiveBT method under two Frozen⁺ settings. As can be seen in the table, the majority of the synthesis time was spent on ITE construction (Step 3) and NaiveBT generation (Step 4), which took much longer time than the Realizability Check (Step 1) and FDS Construction (Step 2). The inefficiency of these two steps lowers the overall method performance. Besides, we didn't present more outcomes of the NaiveBT method since we had already tested it under other scenarios, while it always ran out of time or memory and could only synthesize BTs successfully under the settings in Table. II. Moreover, both the generated BTs have a size of over 100,000, which is extremely large and results in low execution efficiency. **Answer to RQ1 (NaiveBT):** The NaiveBT is not efficient enough, which consumes a lot of time and memory while yielding huge and low-quality BTs.

2) *Results of Other Methods (Synthesis):* Table. III summarizes the evaluated results of the synthesis procedure for various methods, including Spectra, RawBT, EffBT#, and the EffBT, excluding JITS due to its dynamic nature without a construction phase. In this table, the time is measured in *seconds*, and the **bolded** indicates the best result among other methods. The mark *OOT* represents a process that exceeded the maximum allowed time, *N/A* denotes that there are no

TABLE II: Step-by-Step Evaluation Results of the NaiveBT Method under the Frozen⁺ 8×8 and 16×16 Scenario

Task	Frozen ⁺ 8 × 8	Frozen ⁺ 16 × 16
#Nodes (×10k)	0.25	6.37
Step 1: Realizability Check (sec)	0.05	2.10
Step 2: FDS Construction (sec)	0.04	13.38
Step 3: ITE Construction (sec)	0.52	125.26
Step 4: NaiveBT Synthesis (sec)	0.67	144.45
Total Time (sec)	1.28	285.19
BT Size	104392	215346

available values, possibly caused by out of time during the construction phase. Additionally, for each metric evaluated on the SYNTTECH datasets, we represent its value as the average of all tasks within each dataset. Additionally, as illustrated in Table. III, the construction time of RawBT is not restricted by the static FDS construction (Spectra) since we did not follow the expected procedure which obtains FDS first (Step 2) before creating the RawBT (Step 3'). Instead, the BTs were constructed directly from Step 1, but followed the construction of FDS as mentioned in Step 3' during implementation.

The results indicate that our method achieves the shortest construction time across all tasks compared to RawBT and Spectra, with average speedups of 73.8% and 84.7%, respectively. Whether or not EffBT employs pruning strategies, its performance consistently surpasses that of Spectra. Hence, the improvements in synthesis efficiency are mainly attributed to the decomposition of large BDDs. Furthermore, as task specifications become increasingly complex, the construction time of EffBT increases at a much slower rate than that of the other methods. This allows our method to tackle more challenging tasks, while Spectra and JITS struggle. For instance, the Spectra tool timed out in scenarios such as Frozen⁺ 32×32, AMBA_9, and GenBuf_30 to GenBuf_90, the JITS tool also timed out in the Frozen⁺ 32×32 scenario (leading to a N/A when executing). In contrast, our method produced the vast majority of results within minutes and outperformed other methods in terms of construction speed.

3) *Results of Other Methods (Execution):* The simulated execution results of the outcomes produced by Spectra, JITS, RawBT, EffBT, and EffBT# are incorporated in Table. III. In this table, the execution time is an average of the sum of five thousand decision-making steps, measured in *seconds*. We did not execute the BTs synthesized by NaiveBT because their sizes are extremely large (over 100,000).

When comparing the results of EffBT with Spectra and JITS, it is evident that our method significantly reduces decision-making time, showing average performance improvements of 36.0% and 74.0% during randomly simulated executions. Additionally, the execution of EffBT is minimally impacted by the complexity of specifications. This can be attributed to the well-organized small BDDs by using BTs, as well as the pruning of unnecessary BDDs. In scenarios like Frozen⁺, AMBA, and GenBuf, the step time of Spectra and JITS increases as task complexity rises, whereas EffBT maintains consistent execution times at a smaller scale. Then, the execution results for RawBT show that it has the weakest

TABLE III: The Synthesis and Execution Results of Spectra, JITS, RawBT, EffBT#, and our EffBT Methods

Task		#Nodes ($\times 10k$)	Time _{RC} (sec)	Construction Time (sec)				Execution Time (sec)				
				Spectra	RawBT	EffBT	EffBT#	Spectra	JITS	RawBT	EffBT	EffBT#
Frozen ⁺	8 \times 8	0.25	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.09	0.07	0.06	0.20	0.07
	16 \times 16	6.37	2.20	13.71	16.13	11.80	12.03	0.35	0.21	0.26	0.05	0.07
	24 \times 24	49.22	31.19	280.62	1089.12	258.06	271.94	0.78	0.51	0.67	0.05	0.04
	32 \times 32	118.12	131.96	OOT	5711.29	2126.25	2193.02	N/A	N/A	1.28	0.03	0.05
AMBA	AMBA_1	0.19	0.08	0.04	0.02	0.003	0.01	0.03	0.15	0.04	0.03	0.03
	AMBA_3	4.09	6.96	31.91	5.64	0.48	0.49	0.03	0.92	0.05	0.04	0.04
	AMBA_5	14.21	59.11	1511.72	47.38	0.31	1.71	0.05	2.03	0.06	0.03	0.05
	AMBA_7	27.05	332.83	4370.71	81.46	0.91	1.89	0.06	3.25	0.10	0.02	0.06
	AMBA_9	65.15	894.92	OOT	187.32	44.77	48.04	N/A	6.93	0.25	0.01	0.20
GenBuf	GenBuf_10	0.51	0.13	0.23	0.49	0.04	0.10	0.34	0.55	0.64	0.05	0.34
	GenBuf_30	1.99	1.75	OOT	10.38	0.74	1.43	N/A	2.26	0.82	0.05	0.49
	GenBuf_50	4.12	6.66	OOT	53.05	3.18	8.86	N/A	5.84	1.09	0.05	0.59
	GenBuf_70	7.24	17.03	OOT	212.69	5.35	15.61	N/A	11.03	0.72	0.05	0.49
	GenBuf_90	10.94	42.49	OOT	363.15	9.70	29.55	N/A	17.26	0.82	0.05	0.66
SYNTECH	SYNTECH 15	0.20	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.13	0.34	0.19	0.10	0.12
	SYNTECH 17	1.42	2.57	1.37	6.39	0.22	1.05	0.58	0.91	0.78	0.18	0.21
	SYNTECH 19	0.79	0.08	2.20	157.43	0.96	1.18	3.38	8.95	3.82	3.01	11.33
	SYNTECH 20	0.83	0.49	6.69	2.91	0.05	0.13	1.01	1.57	1.31	0.46	0.55
	SYNTECH 21	5.11	22.82	13.15	150.97	1.21	4.14	1.55	2.96	2.04	0.22	0.29

786 decision-making process when compared to the EffBT and
 787 EffBT# methods. The disparity becomes even more evident
 788 as the runtime increases. This phenomenon confirms our
 789 earlier perspective on RawBT, i.e., its structure inherently adds
 790 unnecessary ticks, which results in wasted execution time.

791 **Answer to RQ2:** Our method outperforms others in
 792 both the construction and execution efficiency of synthesized
 793 results, showing significant improvements in time consumption
 794 compared to RawBT, Spectra, and JITS. Meanwhile, its per-
 795 formance is less affected by the complexity of specifications.

796 D. Behavior Tree Quality Results

797 Table. IV presents the quality evaluation results of the BTs
 798 synthesized using the RawBT, EffBT, and EffBT# methods.
 799 Firstly, considering the size of BTs, our method demonstrates
 800 a considerable reduction of nearly half compared to RawBT,
 801 with an average reduction comes to 40.3%. Then, regarding
 802 the BT balance, we observe that although RawBT has similar
 803 or better node balances compared to EffBT, it is lacking in
 804 structural balance. This indicates that the sizes of the subtrees
 805 under their root nodes vary significantly, which are not well-
 806 designed BTs. Taking the Frozen⁺ 32 \times 32 as an example, the
 807 structural balance of RawBT is 0.04, due to the minimum
 808 and maximum sizes of the subtrees being 157 and 3,910
 809 respectively, resulting in a 25-fold difference between them,
 810 which demonstrates an extreme structural imbalance among
 811 the subtrees. In comparison, EffBT has a structural balance of
 812 0.73 (83/113). Our method fixes this drawback and achieves
 813 a better structural balance and tree size, which benefits from
 814 the design of structurally similar subtrees. The average of the
 815 structural balance of RawBT is 0.12, while for the EffBT
 816 method, it rises to 0.68. Regarding the balance of nodes, which
 817 estimates the balance of the *ControlFlow* nodes and the *Execu-*
 818 *tion* nodes, EffBT performs similarly to RawBT, with average
 819 values of 0.57 and 0.58, respectively. Therefore, in summary,
 820 our method demonstrates improved balance and modularity
 821

822 compared to RawBT. **Answer to RQ3:** Our method is capable
 823 of producing high-quality BTs. The generated BTs are smaller
 824 in size owing to our pruning strategies, and exhibit improved
 825 balance and modularity thanks to the construction algorithm.
 826 These factors contribute to more efficient executions of BTs.

827 In addition to the quality results of RawBT, combining
 828 the previous analysis of it in aspects of synthesis efficiency
 829 and simulated execution performance (c.f., Sec. V-C2 and
 830 Sec. V-C3), we could conclude, **Answer to RQ1 (RawBT):**
 831 The RawBT method has a long construction time compared
 832 to ours during BT synthesis but produces BT with reduced
 833 quality, particularly in the imbalance among subtrees, which
 834 adversely affects the execution performance of these BTs.

835 E. Ablation Study Results

836 We investigate the practical effect of our pruning strategies
 837 by comparing EffBT# (EffBT without Pruning Strategies) with
 838 the EffBT method in terms of construction, simulated execu-
 839 tion, and BT structures. Likewise, the experimental results are
 840 summarized in Table. III and Table. IV.

841 Concerning construction time, the findings indicate that in
 842 various scenarios, including AMBA, GenBuf, and the larger
 843 SYNTECH dataset, the pruning strategy consistently leads to
 844 a construct time reduction, with an average decrease of 46.4%.
 845 Then, regarding the execution results of pruned and unpruned
 846 BTs (c.f., Table. III), the unpruned BTs always incur longer
 847 decision-making costs, as the time is wasted on checking
 848 meaningless condition nodes and switching between redundant
 849 structures. At last, in reference to the quality results presented
 850 in Table. IV, it is noteworthy that pruning brings an average
 851 size reduction of 56.1% compared to the unpruned version,
 852 and it performs consistently well across all tasks. As for the
 853 balance of BTs, the results suggest that the impact of pruning
 854 is somewhat limited. The overall balance of EffBT and EffBT#
 855 remains nearly the same, while the node balance of the pruned
 856 BTs (EffBT) is slightly improved.

TABLE IV: Behavior Tree Quality Results of RawBT, EffBT#, and our EffBT Methods

Task		BT Size			Balance (Structural + Nodes')		
		RawBT	EffBT	EffBT#	RawBT	EffBT	EffBT#
Frozen ⁺	8 × 8	89	42	95	0.80 (0.12+0.68)	1.69 (1.00+0.69)	1.45 (1.00+0.45)
	16 × 16	839	408	939	0.93 (0.07+ 0.86)	1.63 (0.82+0.81)	1.29 (0.81+0.48)
	24 × 24	3464	1698	3924	0.96 (0.05+ 0.91)	1.62 (0.76+0.86)	1.24 (0.75+0.49)
	32 × 32	7861	3871	8966	0.97 (0.04+ 0.93)	1.62 (0.73+0.89)	1.22 (0.73+0.49)
AMBA	AMBA_1	185	124	170	0.61 (0.11+0.50)	1.10 (0.44+0.66)	0.89 (0.39+0.50)
	AMBA_3	473	354	442	0.58 (0.09+0.49)	0.82 (0.32+0.50)	0.80 (0.31+0.49)
	AMBA_5	741	552	694	0.59 (0.09+ 0.50)	0.82 (0.32+0.50)	0.81 (0.31+ 0.50)
	AMBA_7	1009	750	946	0.59 (0.09+ 0.50)	0.82 (0.32+0.50)	0.81 (0.31+ 0.50)
	AMBA_9	1277	948	1198	0.58 (0.09+0.49)	0.82 (0.32+0.50)	0.81 (0.31+ 0.50)
GenBuf	GenBuf_10	531	330	484	0.60 (0.13+0.47)	1.22 (0.74+0.48)	1.16 (0.68+ 0.48)
	GenBuf_30	1471	910	1344	0.61 (0.13+ 0.48)	1.22 (0.74+0.48)	1.16 (0.68+ 0.48)
	GenBuf_50	2411	1490	2204	0.62 (0.13+ 0.49)	1.21 (0.74+0.47)	1.16 (0.68+0.48)
	GenBuf_70	3351	2070	3064	0.63 (0.13+ 0.50)	1.21 (0.74+0.47)	1.16 (0.68+0.48)
	GenBuf_90	4291	2650	3924	0.64 (0.13+ 0.51)	1.21 (0.74+0.47)	1.16 (0.68+0.48)
SYNTECH	SYNTECH 15	109	55	100	0.65 (0.17+ 0.48)	1.35 (0.88+0.47)	1.34 (0.88+0.46)
	SYNTECH 17	433	286	426	0.74 (0.13+ 0.61)	1.32 (0.75+0.57)	1.28 (0.75+0.53)
	SYNTECH 19	453	249	431	0.77 (0.26+ 0.51)	1.36 (0.90+0.46)	1.34 (0.89+0.45)
	SYNTECH 20	334	144	331	0.75 (0.17+ 0.58)	1.30 (0.78+0.52)	1.29 (0.78+0.51)
	SYNTECH 21	315	161	338	0.81 (0.19+ 0.63)	1.46 (0.85+0.61)	1.27 (0.84+0.43)

Answer to RQ4: The pruning strategies are crucial for reducing the size of BTs and accelerating both the construction and BT execution periods. Removing them from our method would significantly degrade performance.

VI. RELATED WORKS

Over the past few decades, several methodologies, including Evolutionary Algorithms [1][2], Reinforcement Learning [3], Large Languages Models [5][6], Back-chaining [22], Monte-Carlo Tree Search [23], and Learning from Demonstrations [7][8][24], have been employed for synthesizing BTs and have been applied on various domains such as robot arms and unmanned aerial vehicles. Compared to the learning-based or searching-based methods above, reactive synthesis, which generates controllers that are guaranteed to be correct by construction from formal specifications, exhibits significant advantages in correctness guarantee.

There are two prevailing categories in the context of generating BTs through reactive synthesis: general-LTL-based and F-LTL-based. The former, such as TAMP[4], models the robot-environment interactions as a transition system while transforming task specifications (described by LTL) into Büchi automata simultaneously. Then, it searches for a counter-example path in the product of the transition system and the Büchi automaton. If findable, the final BT is subsequently constructed to equivalently embody the counter-example path. However, due to the EXPTIME complexity of converting LTL to Büchi automata, these methods inevitably suffer problems such as state space explosion and exponential time complexity.

The latter, operated on LTL fragments instead of general LTL, avoids the intractable complexity (at least EXPTIME). Such as [9], it contains six types of LTL patterns which are responsible for different properties, including concepts like ‘globally stands’ and ‘response to a signal’. For each LTL

pattern, there is a corresponding BT template. The BT synthesis process involves combining those templates following the manner of the provided LTL specifications. However, this approach invariably yields a flat BT structure with subtrees of varying sizes, due to the absence of support for nested formulas and the irregularity of BT patterns. Although each subtree correlated with a pattern carries a specific meaning, the assembled behavior tree remains challenging to comprehend. Similar limitations were also noticed in [10]. Attributed to the regularity of GR(1) intermediates, the subtrees in our method have similar structures but are responsible for different justice goals, avoiding the limitations in the aforementioned methods. This design not only aligns with the experience accumulated from previous manual designs but also adheres to software engineering principles, including modularity, performance, readability, and maintainability.

Additionally, compared to the Static [12] and the Just-in-time GR(1) [13] controller synthesizer, our method decomposes the large BDDs into smaller BDDs and combines them using BTs in a well-structured way while keeping the consistency of semantics.

VII. CONCLUSION

We propose an efficient framework for the reactive synthesis and execution of BTs, termed EffBT, which fixes the drawback of irregular BTs found in earlier studies stemming from their calculation and construction methods. Our approach unifies them into GR(1) realizability check and proposes an algorithm for constructing highly modularized BTs. As a result, we can enhance the execution efficiency of the generated BTs by utilizing the *Parallel* node, while few focused on this aspect. We proved the soundness of EffBT, and experimental results across various scenarios and datasets demonstrate that our method outperforms others in both synthesis speed and quality.

- 924 [1] M. Iovino, J. Styrod, P. Falco, and C. Smith, "Learning behavior trees
925 with genetic programming in unpredictable environments," in *2021 IEEE
926 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE,
927 2021, pp. 4591–4597.
- 928 [2] A. Neupane and M. A. Goodrich, "Learning swarm behaviors using
929 grammatical evolution and behavior trees," in *Proceedings of the Twenty-
930 Eighth International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence, IJCAI
931 2019*. ijcai.org, 2019, pp. 513–520.
- 932 [3] R. Dey and C. Child, "QL-BT: enhancing behaviour tree design and
933 implementation with q-learning," in *2013 IEEE Conference on Computa-
934 tional Intelligence in Games (CIG)*. IEEE, 2013, pp. 1–8.
- 935 [4] S. Li, D. Park, Y. Sung, J. A. Shah, and N. Roy, "Reactive task and
936 motion planning under temporal logic specifications," in *2021 IEEE
937 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE
938 Press, 2021, p. 12618–12624.
- 939 [5] Y. Cao and C. S. G. Lee, "Robot behavior-tree-based task generation
940 with large language models," in *Proceedings of the AAAI 2023 Spring
941 Symposium on Challenges Requiring the Combination of Machine
942 Learning and Knowledge Engineering (AAAI-MAKE 2023)*, vol. 3433,
943 2023.
- 944 [6] F. Li, X. Wang, B. Li, Y. Wu, Y. Wang, and X. Yi, "A study on training
945 and developing large language models for behavior tree generation,"
946 *CoRR*, vol. abs/2401.08089, 2024.
- 947 [7] L. Scherf, K. Fröhlich, and D. Koert, "Learning action conditions for
948 automatic behavior tree generation from human demonstrations," in
949 *Companion of the 2024 ACM/IEEE International Conference on Human-
950 Robot Interaction*, ser. HRI '24. Association for Computing Machinery,
951 2024, p. 950–954.
- 952 [8] K. French, S. Wu, T. Pan, Z. Zhou, and O. C. Jenkins, "Learning
953 behavior trees from demonstration," in *International Conference on
954 Robotics and Automation, ICRA 2019*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 7791–7797.
- 955 [9] M. Colledanchise, R. M. Murray, and P. Ögren, "Synthesis of correct-by-
956 construction behavior trees," in *2017 IEEE/RSJ International Conference
957 on Intelligent Robots and Systems, IROS 2017*. IEEE, 2017, pp. 6039–
958 6046.
- 959 [10] T. G. Tadewos, A. A. Redwan Newaz, and A. Karimoddini,
960 "Specification-guided behavior tree synthesis and execution for coordi-
961 nation of autonomous systems," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol.
962 201, p. 117022, 2022.
- 963 [11] R. Bloem, B. Jobstmann, N. Piterman, A. Pnueli, and Y. Sa'ar, "Synthe-
964 sis of reactive(1) designs," *Journal of Computer and System Sciences*,
965 vol. 78, no. 3, pp. 911–938, 2012, in Commemoration of Amir Pnueli.
- 966 [12] S. Maoz and J. O. Ringert, "Reactive synthesis with spectra: A tutorial,"
967 in *43rd IEEE/ACM International Conference on Software Engineering:
968 Companion Proceedings, ICSE Companion*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 320–321.
- 969 [13] S. Maoz and I. Shevrin, "Just-in-time reactive synthesis," in *35th
970 IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineer-
971 ing, ASE 2020*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 635–646.
- 972 [14] R. E. Bryant, "Symbolic boolean manipulation with ordered binary-
973 decision diagrams," *ACM Comput. Surv.*, vol. 24, no. 3, p. 293–318,
974 sep 1992.
- 975 [15] *EffBT: An Efficient Behavior Tree Reactive Synthesis and Execution
976 Framework (Supplementary Materials)*. Zenodo, Nov. 2024. [Online].
977 Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14241343>
- 978 [16] M. Towers, J. K. Terry, A. Kwiatkowski, J. U. Balis, G. d. Cola,
979 T. Deleu, M. Goulão, A. Kallinteris, A. KG, M. Krimmel, R. Perez-
980 Vicente, A. Pierré, S. Schulhoff, J. J. Tai, A. T. J. Shen, and O. G.
981 Younis, "Gymnasium," Mar. 2023.
- 982 [17] R. Bloem, S. Galler, B. Jobstmann, N. Piterman, A. Pnueli, and
983 M. Weiglhofer, "Interactive presentation: Automatic hardware synthesis
984 from specifications: a case study," in *Proceedings of the Conference
985 on Design, Automation and Test in Europe*, ser. DATE '07. EDA
986 Consortium, 2007, p. 1188–1193.
- 987 [18] R. Bloem, S. J. Galler, B. Jobstmann, N. Piterman, A. Pnueli, and
988 M. Weiglhofer, "Specify, compile, run: Hardware from PSL," in *Pro-
989 ceedings of the Workshop on Compiler Optimization meets Compiler
990 Verification, COCV@ETAPS 2007*, ser. Electronic Notes in Theoretical
991 Computer Science, S. Glesner, J. Knoop, and R. Drechsler, Eds., vol.
992 190, no. 4. Elsevier, 2007, pp. 3–16.
- 993 [19] D. Ma'ayan and S. Maoz, "Using reactive synthesis: An end-to-end ex-
994 ploratory case study," in *2023 IEEE/ACM 45th International Conference
995 on Software Engineering (ICSE)*, 2023, pp. 742–754.
- [20] R. Shalom and S. Maoz, "Which of my assumptions are unnecessary
for realizability and why should i care?" in *2023 IEEE/ACM 45th
International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*, 2023, pp.
221–232.
- [21] M. Colledanchise and P. Ögren, "Behavior trees in robotics and AI: an
introduction," *CoRR*, vol. abs/1709.00084, 2017.
- [22] Z. Cai, M. Li, W. Huang, and W. Yang, "BT expansion: a sound
and complete algorithm for behavior planning of intelligent robots
with behavior trees," in *Thirty-Fifth AAAI Conference on Artificial
Intelligence*. AAAI Press, 2021, pp. 6058–6065.
- [23] W. Hong, Z. Chen, M. Li, Y. Li, P. Huang, and J. Wang, "Formal
verification based synthesis for behavior trees," in *Dependable Software
Engineering. Theories, Tools, and Applications - 9th International
Symposium, SETTA 2023*, vol. 14464. Springer, 2023, pp. 72–91.
- [24] S. Gugliermo, E. Schaffernicht, C. Koniaris, and F. Pecora, "Learning
behavior trees from planning experts using decision tree and logic
factorization," *IEEE Robotics Autom. Lett.*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 3534–3541,
2023.